

Pushing slope- to plateau-type behavior in hard carbon for sodium-ion batteries *via* local structure rearrangement

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Elucidating the microstructure of hard carbon is essential for uncovering the sodium storage mechanism and constructing state-of-the-art hard carbon anodes for sodium-ion batteries. Guided by understanding the crystallization process and inverse materials design principles, we design hard carbon anodes with different local fragments to understand the correlating microstructure of hard carbon and sodium storage behaviors from the commercialization perspective. The sodiation transformation of hard carbon from slope- to plateau-type is realized via a series of local structure rearrangements, including interlayer distance, average crystallite width of graphitic domains, and defect density. We found that the increase in plateau capacity is mainly related to the transition from critical interlayer distance to average crystallite width of graphitic domains control, and is limited by the closed pore volume of hard carbon. During sodiation, the formation of NaF and Na₂O in the slope region, as well as Na₂O₂ and NaO₂ in the plateau region, are always accompanied by the production of Na₂CO₃. This work provides insights into understanding the sodium storage behavior in hard carbon anodes and defines general structural design principles from the slope- to plateau type of hard carbon.

Introduction

With ever-increasing energy demands, sodium-ion batteries (SIBs) have received significant attention due to abundant sodium resources and their potential grid storage application. Their commercial viability largely depends on advancement in materials design, as despite the similarity between lithium and sodium, traditional electrodes for lithium-ion batteries cannot be effectively utilized for SIBs due to slow sodium kinetics and low reaction voltage.^{1, 2} For instance, in the case of anode materials, sodium intercalation in the graphite is limited by the considerable intercalation energy barrier³, while the performance of high-capacity electrode (e.g., Si) is hindered by slow sodium diffusion and a large volume expansion^{4, 5}. In this light, owing to its excellent electrochemical stability, high capacity, and low cost, hard carbon has become an emergent anode material for commercial SIBs.⁶⁻⁸ However, hard carbon electrode usually has low initial Coulombic efficiency and poor rate performance problems^{9, 10}, which is primarily attributed to the irreversible consumption of sodium ions during the formation of solid electrolyte interphase (SEI). While different strategies (such as cross-linking,¹¹⁻¹³ pre-oxidation,¹⁴ optimizing graphitization degree^{15, 16}) have been utilized to tune the properties of hard carbon, the correlation between the microstructure and sodium storage behavior is still poorly understood^{17, 18}. This is mainly due to the complexity of the hard carbon structures that, while experimentally characterized by a broad (002) graphite-like peak, lacks distinct long-range order and exhibit a range of local fragments, ranging from the ratio between sp³/sp² hybridized atoms to different small/large-size pores. Moreover, the spatial distribution of such local fragments plays a critical role: i.e. open pores closely connected to the external surface play a crucial role in ion transport and sodium storage.¹⁹⁻²¹ In contrast, it is believed that closed pores located away from the surface are not directly accessible to electrolyte.

From the commercialization perspective, plateau-type electrodes are strongly preferred over slope-type ones (**Figure 1a**), as the former exhibits a flat, stable voltage profile during the charge/discharge process, ensuring a more consistent and reliable power output (the slope region refers to voltages above 0.1 V, while the plateau region corresponds to voltages below 0.1 V). This implies that tailoring the distribution of local fragments can target such transition. In a typical experiment, hard carbon is prepared by the carbonization of organic precursors (e.g., glucose), where the base material undergoes thermal decomposition during different annealing/equilibration steps.²² From the fundamental theory of crystallization for hard carbon, it becomes evident that the structure of hard carbon is controlled *via* the superposition of the (i) diffusion, (ii) nucleation, and (iii) growth processes, which happen spontaneously during a thermal treatment.^{23, 24} At the diffusion step (i), carbon atoms mainly rearrange within the local structure, while at stage (ii), a range of crystalline-graphite-like nuclear centers is formed, whose size increases further during the growth stage (iii).²⁵ This understanding thus represents that the properties (**P**) of hard carbon are the superposition of properties (**p_i**) of local structures ($\mathbf{P} = \sum_i^n \mathbf{c}_i \mathbf{p}_i$). While the characters of each type of local structures are generally constant, their weight (**c_i**) could be significantly affected by the synthesis protocols (**Figure 1b**).

Our first-principles calculations demonstrate that the defective regions of hard carbon are highly active and expected to contribute to sodium storage only at high voltage (Figure 1c). For example, first-principles calculations predict that Na will be captured by C vacancies in graphene at a potential of 0.67 V. Contrarily, the graphite-like regions with expanded interlayer distance can accommodate sodium ions/metal/clusters in low-voltage plateau regions (Figure 1d), promoting the formation of metallic sodium clusters or islands and providing additional capacity. This fundamental understanding allows us to formulate the theoretically guided design for plateau-type hard carbon (Figure 1e) as: (i) opening interlayer distance (d_{002}) above some critical value enables sodium intercalation; (ii) minimization of point defect density (D) reduces slope region and their role in SEI formation. (iii) average crystallite width (L_a) of the graphitic domain defines the sodium storage capacity for the intercalation-like reaction. To verify our hypothesis and correlate hard carbon microstructure to sodium storage, we synthesize a range of hard carbon structures having different ratios of microstructure parameters (d_{002} , D , and L_a , denoted as d , D , and L for sample titles). In this way, we develop a unique perspective on the local structural rearrangement of hard carbon, allowing us to transform hard carbon from slope-type to plateau-type behavior. Additionally, we introduced a descriptor to capture the correlation between the local structure and plateau capacity based on the evolution process of the superposition and balance of local structural features. This work provides valuable insights into the sodium storage behavior of hard carbon anodes and offers guidance for using local structural rearrangement to enhance performance. For instance, the optimized electrode shows the largest plateau capacity of 215 mAh g⁻¹ and makes up for 73.7% of the total reversible specific capacity of 293 mAh g⁻¹. Furthermore, *in-situ* Raman, XRD, TEM, and ex-situ ²³Na magic-angle-spinning (MAS) solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (ssNMR), and X-ray absorption spectra (XAS) were used to detect the structure evolution during the sodiation/desodiation process. Notably, the plateau region exhibits a variable mass transfer impedance corresponding to the typical intercalation-pore filling model of the sodium storage mechanism. Our results thus confirm the inverse materials design principle, showing that the target hard carbon microstructure exhibits excellent plateau capacity and also provides inspiration for the design of high plateau capacity from the views of the slope type to plateau type hard carbon.

Results and discussion

Taking into account our fundamental understanding of the local structure discussed above, we prepared a set of different hard carbon samples – all having different distributions of local structures generated by the utilization of varying temperature protocols. The idea here is that using different temperature protocols allows for stabilizing the different distributions of local structures, as the time for diffusion, nucleation, and growth is tuned based on the synthesis protocols (Figure 1b-e). Specifically, we have synthesized different hard carbon series with the temperature gradient at 800, 1300, 1500, and 1900 °C undergo the argon atmosphere with 3 h (more details in the experiment section), respectively, which makes it possible to determine the local structural information and track the evolutionary formation mechanism. Additionally, the control sample is stabilized at a low temperature of 500 °C. We note that while hard carbon samples can be abbreviated based on the temperature gradient protocols^{24, 26}. However, to reappraisal the role of the distribution of local structures in the properties of hard carbon, each sample is characterized by d_{002} spacing (d), defect density (D), and average crystallite width (L_a) with variations ranging from extra-large (xs) to extra-small (xs). For instance, the control sample has extra-large d_{002} (d_{xl}), extra-large defect density (D_{xl}), and extra small basal plane width (L_{xs}) and is denoted as $d_{xl}D_{xl}L_{xs}$. The prepared hard carbon samples exhibit an amorphous distribution, characterized by a random structure lacking long-range order, as observed through transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Additionally, it also shows the different structures of closed pores (Figure S1, ESI[†]), which contributed to the evolution of d_{002} , defect density, and L_a of hard carbon. Figure 2a-b and Figure S1-S2, Table S1, ESI[†] show the effect of temperature gradient protocols on the internal properties of hard carbon in this work. It demonstrates that L_a and average thickness (L_c) of the graphitic domains enhance in hard carbon series by boosting the local structure rearrangement. For instance, L_a values of the $d_lD_lL_s$, $d_mD_mL_m$, $d_sD_sL_l$, and $d_{xs}D_{xs}L_{xl}$ samples expand from 2.79 to 6.04 nm (the L_c from 0.88 to 4.13 nm). d_{002} values of hard carbon decrease from 0.389 to 0.351 nm by the results of temperature gradient protocols in Figure 2a, which process is attributed to kinetical control according to the nucleation/growth theory of carbon.²⁷ As the temperature increases, the hard carbon samples become more crystalline due to the removal of the O-containing oxidation group. This tendency is also clearly evident from the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), showing that the enhancement of the proportion of the sp^2/sp^3 section as evident from the analysis of C 1s divided into three peaks of 284.8 (sp^2), 285.9 (sp^3), and 287.9 eV (C=O/C-O) as well as O 1s composited by two peaks of 532.2 (C-O) and 534.6 eV (C=O) (Figure S4-5, ESI[†]).²⁸⁻³⁰ Moreover, the C=O functional group content of the obtained samples is decreased due to the fast kinetics driving force by local structure rearrangement, which leads to a reduction of the active sites in the reaction of $C=O + Na^+ + e^- \leftrightarrow -C-O-Na$ for the sodium storage capacity. Besides, the degree of disorder in the as-prepared samples was further verified by the Raman spectra. The D band (1350 cm⁻¹) represents the A_{1g} mode of sp^2 -hybridized carbon systems caused by respiratory vibration of disordered/defective structure, while the G band (1580 cm⁻¹) corresponds to the expansion mode of sp^2 carbon in the graphite ring/chain. As shown in Figure 2c, Figure S6, Table S2, ESI[†], the $I_D/(I_D+I_G)$ ratio denotes the relative defect density of hard carbon, which shows a decreasing trend from 0.978, 0.932, 0.921, to 0.851, and corresponding to the $d_lD_lL_s$, $d_mD_mL_m$, $d_sD_sL_l$, and $d_{xs}D_{xs}L_{xl}$ samples, respectively. These results, as the proof-of-concept, further clearly prove that the distribution of local structures can be designed by tailoring the kinetics behaviors, including d_{002} , defect density, and L_a parameters of hard carbon series.

Figure 1. The proposed strategy for local structures is designed towards the low-voltage plateau capacity of hard carbon. (a) Slope and plateau-type hard carbon and their corresponding voltage profiles. (b) Hard carbon as a superposition of local structures defined by the equilibration-dependent distribution. (c) Na interaction with C vacancy in graphite with corresponding charge density difference. Blue and yellow regions correspond to charge density decrease and increase. (d) Correlating sodium ion voltage and interlayer distance in the plateau region on example of bilayer graphene. (e) Guideline for the plateau region of sodium storage in hard carbon.

Since the crystalline regions in hard carbon are finite, they are significantly misaligned, resulting in the formation of different-sized pores. To understand such special arrangements, first, the N_2 adsorption-desorption curves were used to elevate the open pore structure. Second, the closed pore structure was estimated by combining small-angle scattering (SAXS) and true density. The close pore results show that the $d_1D_1L_5$ sample exhibits the typical isotherm of type IV, which provides the highest specific surface area of $\sim 28.2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and a total volume of $\sim 0.0297 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ with an average pore size of $\sim 8.37 \text{ nm}$. While the $d_mD_mL_m$, $d_sD_sL_l$, and $d_{x_s}D_{x_s}L_{x_l}$ samples obviously display the micropore structure of those series (the typical I-type isotherm).³¹ These samples show a reductive specific surface area from 4.1 to $3.8 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, a total volume from 0.009 to $0.004 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$, and an average pore size from 5.27 to 3.46 nm compared to the $d_1D_1L_5$ sample (Figure 2d, Table S3, ESI†). The SAXS results demonstrate that the $d_{x_s}D_{x_s}L_{x_l}$ sample exhibits the highest scattering intensities among all the samples, indicating a rich closed pore structure (as illustrated in Figure 2e, where the dotted line represents graphite as a reference standard). The average closed pore sizes for the $d_1D_1L_5$, $d_mD_mL_m$, $d_sD_sL_l$, and $d_{x_s}D_{x_s}L_{x_l}$ samples were found to be 0.62, 0.71, 0.98, and 1.13 nm, respectively. This increase in average pore size can be attributed to the gradual nucleation and growth of the local structures in the hard carbon series (Figure S7, ESI†). The true density,

used to evaluate the closed pore structure, showed a decreasing trend, with values reducing from 2.02 g cm^{-3} for $d_1D_1L_s$ to 1.86 g cm^{-3} for $d_mD_mL_m$, 1.61 g cm^{-3} for $d_sD_sL_l$, and 1.48 g cm^{-3} for $d_{xs}D_{xs}L_{xl}$, as determined by He. These true density measurements further confirm the increasing abundance of closed pores as the local structure evolves. Additionally, based on the open pore structure analysis, the closed pore surface area showed a corresponding increase, with values ranging from $150 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for $d_mD_mL_m$ to $297.9 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for $d_sD_sL_l$, $354 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for $d_{xs}D_{xs}L_{xl}$, and reaching $469 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for $d_1D_1L_s$ (**Figure S8, ESIf**). The $d_{xs}D_{xs}L_{xl}$ sample reveals the highest closed pore volume of $0.233 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ comparison to the other samples of $d_1D_1L_s$ ($0.053 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$), $d_mD_mL_m$ ($0.096 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$), and $d_sD_sL_l$ ($0.179 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$) in **Figure S9, ESIf**. The results show that the closed pore volume gradually increases by the controlling kinetics of local formation, and the closed pore size and pore area also raises from the $d_1D_1L_s$, $d_mD_mL_m$, $d_sD_sL_l$, to and $d_{xs}D_{xs}L_{xl}$ samples.

Figure 2. The graphitic microcrystal and electrochemical characterization for hard carbon in sodium-ion batteries. (a-c) Interlayer distance (d_{002}), average crystallite width (L_a), and defect density (D) of graphitic domains for the hard carbon samples obtained from X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns. (d) N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms and pore size distribution obtained from BJH, (e) the small-angle X-ray scattering profiles (SAXS) of the $d_1D_1L_s$, $d_mD_mL_m$, $d_sD_sL_l$, and $d_{xs}D_{xs}L_{xl}$ samples. (f) discharge and charge curves at the first cycle of the obtained samples at current density 0.05 A g^{-1} . (g) The rate performance of the $d_1D_1L_s$, $d_mD_mL_m$, $d_sD_sL_l$, and $d_{xs}D_{xs}L_{xl}$ samples at different currents from 0.05 to 5.0 A g^{-1} . (h) The cycling number performance at current density 0.5 A g^{-1} of the $d_1D_1L_s$, $d_mD_mL_m$, $d_sD_sL_l$, and $d_{xs}D_{xs}L_{xl}$ samples.

The prepared hard carbon samples have been to better understand the role of local structure in SIB anodes by their electrochemical performance (**Figure 2f-g**). The results demonstrate that all samples have slope and plateau regions in the voltage profile. However, there is a significant difference in sodium storage performance for different samples. The $d_sD_sL_l$ shows the largest specific capacity of 293 mAh g^{-1} at a current density of 0.05 A g^{-1} , while the $d_1D_1L_s$ sample delivers only 114 mAh g^{-1} . As the charge rate increases, the $d_sD_sL_l$ sample still demonstrates superior performance among all considered samples (the $d_mD_mL_m$ has a slightly higher capacity than $d_sD_sL_l$ only at 5.0 A g^{-1}). To gain further understanding, we have employed the cyclic voltammetry method to highlight the kinetics behavior among samples at different scanning rates. The results show that the $d_sD_sL_l$ exhibits outstanding reversible curves and a high capacitive process of 92.31% at the scan rate of 1.0 mV s^{-1} , which implies excellent kinetic behavior (**Figure S10-11, ESIf**). According to the dQ/dV curves at 0.05 A g^{-1} from 0.005 V to 2.0 V, the $d_mD_mL_m$ shows the lowest overpotential of $\sim 18.7 \text{ mV}$ ($d_sD_sL_l \sim 37.7 \text{ mV}$, $d_{xs}D_{xs}L_{xl} \sim 56.6 \text{ mV}$) among these samples (**Figure S12, ESIf**), suggesting the smallest nucleation potential in the plateau region.³² The $d_sD_sL_l$ sample demonstrates excellent cycling stability, with almost no capacity loss observed over 300 charge-discharge cycles at a current density of 0.5 A g^{-1} (**Figure 2h**). Additionally, the $d_sD_sL_l$ sample shows strong capacity contributions from both the slope and plateau regions of the voltage profile, indicating efficient sodium storage across different

voltage ranges. Therefore, we have chosen the $d_3D_5L_1$ sample for further analysis to understand the Na storage mechanisms that occur specifically in the slope and plateau regions.

Figure 3. The evolution process of storage sodium behaviors from the slope to plateau region of hard carbon. (a) Schematic illustration of the *in-situ* TEM setup utilizing $d_3D_5L_1$ hard carbon (HC) electrode, with an Al foil as the current, Na metal as the counter electrode, and Na_2O on Na surface as the solid electrolyte. (b-f) *In-situ* TEM images of the $d_3D_5L_1$ electrode at different times (0-12 minutes). (b'-g') The *ex-situ* TEM diffraction patterns at different potentials stages: (b') 2.0 V, (c') 1.0 V, (d') 0.5 V, (e') 0.1 V, (f') 0.01 V, (g') -0.01 V. (h-k) The local electronic structure of $d_3D_5L_1$ during the first discharge process at different stages. (h) Na K-edge, and (i) O K-edge XANES spectra, (j) Na K-edge EXAFS spectra (the inset figure is Na_2CO_3 crystallographic information file), and (k) fitting result of coordination number (CN) and bond length (R) of Na-O. (l-o) The wavelet transforms of EXAFS signals of $d_3D_5L_1$ at different discharge states (100 mV, 50 mV, 10 mV, 0 mV).

To further elucidate the sodium storage mechanism of hard carbon in the slope region and low-voltage plateau region, we employed *in-situ* TEM to characterize the evolution of sodium storage in hard carbon at different discharge potentials (**Figure 3a**). As discharge depth increases, the $d_sD_sL_i$ electrode surface appears to have a significantly deepened shadow region (**Figure 3b-g**), indicating that sodium ions continue to enter the hard carbon interior, corresponding to the increased sodium storage capacity.³³⁻³⁵ In addition, the sodium evolution forms at different potentials were understood by *ex-situ* TEM. Initially, in the high-voltage range of 2.0-1.0 V, sodium ions are primarily absorbed on the surface of hard carbon through the defect and active sites, corresponding to the typical amorphous diffraction ring (**Figure 3b'-c'**). In the medium voltage range of 1.0-0.1 V, the NaF, Na₂O, and Na₂CO₃ were observed at 0.5 V, corresponding to the lattice planes (311), (220), and (310), respectively (**Figure 3d'**). Upon discharge at 0.1 V, the formation of Na₂O₂ and Na₂CO₃ is observed, as indicated by the lattice planes (220) and (102), respectively (**Figure 3e'**, **Figure S13**, **ESI†**). At the same time, sodium ions are gradually embedded into the micropores and nanopores of hard carbon. As the potential is further reduced, sodium ions begin to embed between the layers of hard carbon, forming a stable sodiated carbon phase in the plateau region of the voltage profile.³⁶ At a discharge potential of 0.01 V, the NaF, NaO₂, and Na₂CO₃ are identified corresponding to the lattice planes (100), (112), and (310) (**Figure 3e'**, **Figure S14**, **ESI†**), respectively. Subsequently, when the voltage is reduced to -0.01 V, the Na, NaO₂, and Na₂CO₃ are detected based on the (100), (020), and (112) lattice planes (**Figure 3f'**, **Figure S15**, **ESI†**), respectively, indicating the formation of sodium metal, which is consistent with the solid-state nuclear magnetic results.³⁷

To gain a deeper understanding of the sodium storage behavior in hard carbon, we have investigated the $d_sD_sL_i$ electrode under different discharge potentials by *ex-situ* synchrotron X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS). The Na K-edge adsorption energy gradually decreases from 100 to 0 mV, indicating that the reductive state of sodium ion is enhanced (**Figure 3h**).^{38, 39} Simultaneously, the O K-edge also shifts towards lower energy (**Figure 3i**), reflecting an increase in the Na-O coordination number. Notably, the Na K-edge absorption energy curve closely resembles that of Na₂CO₃, rather than Na₂O₂, suggesting the formation of Na₂CO₃ throughout the discharge process. Additionally, at 0 mV, the O K-edge absorption energy near the edge is more similar to Na₂O₂, indicating the presence of both Na₂O₂ and Na₂CO₃. Furthermore, the structure evolution was investigated by the extended X-ray fine spectrum analysis (EXAFS) combined with fitting results at different potentials (**Figure 3j-k**, **Figure S16**, **ESI†**). With the increase of discharge depth, the Na-O path is almost maintained, and accompanied by the gradual rise of the Na-O bond from 2.29 Å to 2.40 Å, which made up with the embedding of sodium into hard carbon process, and followed by a slight change, corresponding to the filling process of sodium ions.⁴⁰ It is important to note that the adjacent coordination structure exhibits a disordered trend around 100 mV, resulting in an unusual increase in the coordination number. With decreasing potential, the coordination number reveals the stable state, which matches the formation of smaller sodium clusters. The wavelet transform is also used to identify the type and bond length of coordination atoms by their K and R space dependency (**Figure 3l-o**, **Table S4**, **ESI†**). It shows the first increase and then decrease trend coordination number of Na-O, which clearly describes the adsorption-intercalation and filling processes of sodium ions in hard carbon, providing in-depth evidence for the pore-filling mechanism in hard carbon. The formation of Na-Na bonds was not detected during the process, possibly due to the transient sodium exposure in the *ex-situ* XAS.

Figure 4. Charge-storage kinetics analysis and sodium-storage mechanism for the obtained electrodes in the range of 0.005-2.0 V. (a) Estimated sodium ions diffusion coefficients from the GITT potential profiles of $d_5D_5L_1$ electrode for the sodiation/desodiation process. (b) *In-situ* EIS curves of $d_5D_5L_1$ electrode at discharging stage from 2.0 V to 0.005 V. (c-d) The distribution of relaxation times (DRT) plots (τ_1 , τ_2 , τ_3) obtained by deconvolving the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) during the discharging process, the different stages of the contour plots of DRTs for (c, e) UHC and (d, f) $d_5D_5L_1$ electrodes. (g-h) Ex situ ^{23}Na MAS NMR spectra of $d_5D_5L_1$ electrode at different discharge states (50 mV, 10 mV, 0 mV). (i) *In-situ* Raman spectra and (j) *In-situ* XRD pattern of $d_5D_5L_1$ electrode during the first charge/discharge at a current density of 50 mA g^{-1} .

Based on the above results, it is found that the local structure of hard carbon is an evaluated parameter regulating the behavior of sodium storage from the slope region to the plateau region. To further understand the correlation between the microstructure of hard carbon and sodium storage behavior, we investigated the diffusion coefficients of sodium ions in the obtained hard carbon series by the galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT). The results indicate that all samples show staged diffusion coefficients that vary between 2.0 and 0.005 V (Figure 4a, Figure S17, ES1†). Moreover, it shows that the enhanced diffusion coefficients from 2.0 to 0.1 V correspond to the electrolyte decomposition and the SEI formation. Furthermore, as the boundary line at 0.1 V, there is a typical trend of first decreasing and then increasing below 0.1 V, which is assigned to the transformation of

the sodium storage mechanism in the plateau region.^{41, 42} To distinguish the mechanism of sodium storage in the slope region and plateau region, the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) of the prepared hard carbon series and $d_{x1}D_{x1}L_{x5}$ samples were analyzed by the distribution of relaxation times (DRT) during the discharge process (**Figure 4b-d**, **Figure S18**, **ESI†**). The τ_1 represents the contact impedance of the electrode, and the τ_2 conforms to the SEI impedance formed, while the τ_3 is aligned with the charge transfer impedance.⁴³⁻⁴⁵ The plateau-type $d_5D_5L_1$ sample exhibits an increased relaxation time with a further discharge process related to the evolutive sodium diffusion coefficients. However, the slope type $d_{x1}D_{x1}L_{x5}$ sample demonstrates a fixed relaxation time matching the adsorption process from 0.2 to 0.01 V, with a clear trend corresponding to the contour diagrams (**Figure 4e-f**). Based on the above results, through observing the evolution process of the sodium ion diffusion coefficient, it was discovered that the evolution process of the relaxation time corresponds to the evolution behavior of the sodium storage mechanism in hard carbon. In this context, the ^{23}Na MAS NMR can be employed to reveal the storage state of sodium across various discharge stages of 100, 50, 10, and 0 mV (**Figure 4g-h**). Furthermore, a notable broad peak rather than a singular sharp peak emerges with a shift from approximately 700 to 1000 ppm due to the Knight shift and quasi-metallic sodium clusters.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ Additionally, the sodium storage mechanism of $d_5D_5L_1$ electrode was further evaluated by *in-situ* Raman and XRD. The G-band shows a redshift, indicating electron transfer and ion insertion into the graphitic domains as the material transitions from the slope region to the plateau region (**Figure 4i**). Meanwhile, the D-band exhibits a slight weakening during the discharge process.⁴⁹ Notably, the charging process displays distinct reversibility. This is in good agreement with *in-situ* XRD analysis of the graphitic domains in the $d_5D_5L_1$ sample, revealing that the graphite (002) peak at 26° remains virtually unchanged, with no new diffraction peaks appearing throughout the entire charge-discharge cycle (**Figure 4j**). However, the SEI layer, which forms on the surface of hard carbon, contains sodium-containing species (e.g., NaF, Na_2O , and Na_2CO_3). While these species are detected in *in-situ* TEM based on their lattice planes, they do not produce characteristic peaks in the *in-situ* XRD results. This discrepancy arises because *in-situ* TEM can detect surface features at a depth of a few nm (i.e., SEI-rich region). In contrast, *in-situ* XRD detects diffraction signals from the entire material surface, typically covering a depth of 1-10 μm . Furthermore, the SEI layer formed on the surface of hard carbon has a relatively low content of these sodium-containing species, making them difficult for *in-situ* XRD detection. Based on these results, the obtained $d_5D_5L_1$ sample exhibits the interlayer embedding and quasi-metal clusters formed by the pore-filling mechanism, which shows the typical adsorption- intercalation- pore filling model for the sodium storage mechanism.

Figure 5. Unlocking the correlation between local structure distribution and plateau capacity from the slope type to plateau type of hard carbon for sodium ion batteries. (a) Correlation between closed pore volume and plateau capacity. (b) Correlation between the sodium volume fraction filled and the closed volume. (c-f) The influence factors composed of graphitization degree, defect density, and closed pore structure as the key parameters to determine the plateau capacity. (c) The plateau capacity correlations with d_{002} , (d) L_a of graphitic domains and closed pore volume. (e) The plateau capacity correlations with d_{002} , (f) L_a of graphitic domains and closed pore size. (g) The guideline evolution of hard carbon from slope type to plateau type for sodium ion batteries.

There are already some works that have presented promising prospects in the sodium storage mechanism of hard carbon.¹⁹⁻²¹ Zhao et al.²⁰ have studied the relationship between the structural properties of hard carbon and its electrochemical performance, and found that a large interlayer spacing along with small and thin pseudographite domains are conducive to the easy intercalation of sodium ion. Through a detailed analysis of three commercial hard carbon products via *in-situ* X-ray diffraction and Raman measurements, the adsorption-intercalation-filling mechanism is validated as a convincing explanation for the varying sodium storage behaviors. Inspired by amorphous alloys, Bai et al.⁶ have proposed and confirmed the dispersion region at the junction between amorphous structures and graphite microcrystals, which is closely related to the structure of graphite microcrystals. In addition, Yun et al.⁵⁰ have designed the capacity utilization coefficient of high plateau capacity to study the close relationship between the intensity ratio of 2D and G bands (I_{2D}/I_G) in Raman spectrum and the internal dynamic barrier of sodium ion transfer. However, the sodium storage products have been understood in depth, neither in the sloping region nor in the plateau region, which is particularly important for revealing the storage behavior of sodium in hard carbon. In light of these challenges, to further understand material properties and the sodium storage mechanism, a ratio of capacities for plateau and slope regions has been calculated for each sample utilizing 0.1 V as the dividing line. The results summarized in **Figure S19, ESI†** show that in addition to different distributions of local structures, there is a district difference in sodium storage mechanism in different samples. With the increase of closed pore structure, the plateau capacity showed a trend of first increasing and then decreasing, increasing from 77 mAh g⁻¹ (41.8%) of $d_1D_1L_5$ to 215 mAh g⁻¹ (81.7%) of $d_5D_5L_1$, and then reducing to 210 mAh g⁻¹ (82.6%) of $d_{xS}D_{xS}L_{xI}$. These findings further support the notion that certain sections of the closed pore structure do not contribute to sodium storage in the plateau region, which aligns with the results for the closed pore volume. Moreover, the slope region ratio exhibits decreased trends in the as-prepared samples due to the adsorption of sodium ions and the shrunken defect density. In addition, to clarify the correlation between the plateau capacity and the closed pore volume of hard carbon. The results show that the closed pore volume is maintained between 0.053-0.233 cm³ g⁻¹ (**Figure 5a, Figure S9, ESI†**), and the plateau capacity shows a trend of first increasing and then stabilizing or slightly decreasing with the increase of closed pore volume. Moreover, the closed pore size and area also show similar phenomena (**Figure S20, ESI†**). The correlation between the volume fraction of sodium metal/clusters filled in different samples and the closed pore volume was shown in **Figure 5b, Table S5, ESI†**. With the increase of L_a and L_c , and the decrease in defect density, the closed pore volume gradually increases, and the corresponding sodium storage capacity also shows a trend of first increasing and then decreasing from the slope-type to the plateau-type of hard carbon charge-discharge curve. Because the aggregation reaction of sodium storage in hard carbon in the plateau region is limited by the closed pore volume, the plateau capacity changes accordingly.^{51, 52} In this context, even if the closed pore volume continues to increase, its plateau capacity will not continue to increase. Additionally, the local structure rearrangement significantly affects the micropore structure and graphitization degree and defect density of hard carbon, and the $S_{closed\ pore}$ reflects the closed pore parameters of the samples. We further proposed a descriptor that can describe the relationship between plateau capacity and closed pore structure in formula (1).

$$P_i = G_i \times \frac{I_D}{I_D + I_G} \times S_{closed\ pore} \quad (1)$$

$$G1 = \frac{0.389 - d_{002}}{0.389 - 0.3354} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

$$G2 = \frac{6.09 - L_a}{6.09 - 2.79} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

P_i is denoted as plateau capacity for hard carbon series. G_i is evaluated standard of graphitization degree, measured by d_{002} ($G1$) and L_a ($G2$) in formula (2-3). Notley, d_{002} of 0.389 nm, 0.3354 nm represents the $d_1D_1L_5$ and the standard graphene, while L_a of 6.09 nm, 2.79 nm assigns the $d_{xS}D_{xS}L_{xI}$, $d_1D_1L_5$ samples, respectively (**Table S1, ESI†**). $\frac{I_D}{I_D + I_G}$ represents the ratio of defect density along the whole graphitic domains. $S_{closed\ pore}$ including closed pore volume, and closed pore volume size.

The general descriptor is difficult to directly consider the plateau capacity of hard carbon, which is attributed to the unique d_{002} and L_a of the as-prepared hard carbon series. Also, the evaluate factor of the graphitization degree, the closed pore structure and the defects density of hard carbon jointly affect the plateau capacity for sodium ion storage.^{50, 53} High defect density accompanied by ultra-high d_{002} above 0.40 nm and high active sites always results in lots of electrolyte decomposition, which can provide large slope capacity and small or barely plateau capacity. As d_{002} reduces and L_a rises, the defect density diminishes and the closed pore volume increases, which could accommodate many sodium ions and sodium metal/clusters in the plateau region. As a proof-of-concept, to support this concept, we have introduced microstructure parameter graphitization degree (d_{002} and L_a , denoted as $G1$ and $G2$, respectively) and defect density in the formula (2-3). As shown in **Figure 5c-d**, based on the formulas (1-3), the factor ($G1, V$) represents the plateau capacity correlations with d_{002} of graphitic domains and closed pore volume (denoted as V). Notley, the correlation between $G1, G2$, and closed pore volume exhibits the determination coefficient (R^2) values are 0.909 ($G1, V$) and 0.931 ($G2, V$) in the obtained hard carbon series, respectively, which indicates the satisfied correlation coefficient. In addition, we also investigated the correlation between $G1, G2$, and closed pore size (denoted as S), showing a correlation coefficient of 0.761 ($G1, S$) and 0.937 ($G2, S$), respectively, in **Figure 5e-f**. Combined with these results, it can be found that L_a plays a dominant role in the influence of plateau capacity. Therefore, we propose that the high plateau capacity should be a high

graphitization degree (large L_a), decreased defect density, and satisfied closed pore volume. Based on the computational and experimental results above, achieving high capacity (both high plateau and high slope capacities) requires a rational design that optimizes defect density in future work. We believe that there are two processes for hard carbon, from slope type to plateau type (Figure 5g). First, at small d_{002} (below 0.36 nm), Na intercalation between graphite layers is limited, limiting Na storage without a plateau region. Due to the high activity of defect sites, the adsorption process preferentially occurs, including edge and defect sites, which corresponds to apparent slope-type hard carbon. Second, d_{002} of hard carbon gradually shrinks (0.36-0.40 nm) due to the local structure rearrangement, allowing the formation of a plateau region at low potential. Also, compared with the slope-type hard carbon, L_a of the obtained hard carbon gradually increases, the degree of graphitization increases, and the defect density decreases. In this context, obtaining the maximum plateau region requires increasing L_a and reducing the defect density, which is dominated by L_a .

Conclusion

In summary, we systematically explored the role of local structures in sodium ion storage behavior by the fundamental understanding of the charge/discharge process of hard carbon. We defined the inverse materials design principles to push slope-type to plateau-type sodium ion storage *via* an understanding of the crystallization process during hard carbon preparation. We identify that due to the finite size of graphitic domains resulting in unique spatial arrangements, opening the interlayer distance between graphite-like layers results in thermodynamically favorable Na intercalation at low voltages, while sodium ion storage on defects is usually attributed to high voltage. Hence, by minimizing the defect concentration, the slope capacity can be significantly reduced, while the plateau capacity here is found to be defined by geometric properties of graphite domains (i.e., the average crystallite width of the graphitic domain, and the closed pores volume). In particular, there are obvious differences in sodium storage behaviors; NaF and Na₂O are produced in the slope region, while Na₂O₂ and NaO₂ are produced in the plateau region, and Na₂CO₃ is always present during sodiation. This work also highlights the association between fundamental local structure and sodium storage for plateau regions of hard carbon, paving the way for the design of ultra-high plateau capacity of hard carbon anodes in the high energy density of SIBs.

Author contributions

F. W. designed and performed of the experiments including material synthesis, structural characterization, and electrochemical measurements. L. C., and F. L. devoted to the sample preparation and electrochemical data analysis. O. M. contributed to the DFT calculations. J. W., C. D. devoted to the XAS data analysis. C. D. conducted *in-situ* TEM characterization. X. B., Y. T., X. C, O. M., Z. B., and Y. Z. revised the manuscript. All authors discussed and contributed to the writing.

Data availability

The data supporting this paper have been included as part of the ESI.†

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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